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**Embattled Minds: An Investigation of Climate Trauma in John Lanchester's
The Wall and Sarah K. Jackson's *Not Alone***

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Abstract:

This paper focuses on how the perception of catastrophic climate scenarios can influence the mental health and trauma response of individuals who are affected by climate change-related events. Climate change and environmental disasters cause psychological effects that lead to emotional distress and mental health impacts, known as climate trauma. The present study aims to examine the psychological impact of climate disasters. The study evaluates the impacts of climate change narratives in the societal space by comparing the portrayal of climate trauma in the chosen texts. The climate trauma-based novels explore the responsibilities of human beings and other species, delving into the depths of dystopian despair and moments of hope while underscoring the gradual destruction of the planet. This study highlights the impact of shifting climate conditions

on the mental health of victims, indicating a need for improved mental health services and further research on its effects.

Keywords: Climate trauma, climate change, eco-anxiety, solastalgia, ecological grief, social isolation.

Man and nature share a profound relationship, relying on each other with a proper balance and interconnectedness. Climate conditions play a vital role in shaping nature, making it a comfortable place for habitation and vegetation by regulating the temperature. Nevertheless, extreme climate changes pose a serious threat to a resilient and sustainable future for all living beings. This research focuses on providing a deeper insight into the impact of climate change, particularly on human psychology and nature as a whole, by exploring the genre of climate fiction or Cli-fi. As individuals encounter physical changes regarding climate, they are also prone to severe mental conditions including eco-anxiety, grief, emotional distress and post-traumatic stress, which fall under the umbrella term 'climate trauma'. Therefore, the study affirms that the adverse effects of climate change can negatively impact human mental health. *The Wall*, John Lanchester depicts a future dystopia where a concrete barrier traps millions of climate migrants, forcing them to float endlessly in the sea outside it. *Not Alone* by Sarah K. Jackson explores a post-apocalyptic world devastated by environmental disasters, which focuses on the psychological effects of climate trauma, especially on a mother-child relationship.

Joseph Kavanagh, the protagonist of *The Wall*, narrates the novel from a first-person perspective as he serves as a defender of the Wall in near-future Britain. Approximately 50,000 defenders are assigned to guard the Wall and are tasked with keeping out the Others. Extreme climate change causes sea levels to rise, trapping the Others outside the Wall. Through his narration of the story of the Wall and its surrounding characters, Lanchester examines the social and

psychological effects of climate change. To pacify their anguish, the characters use storytelling as a wall of resistance.

The reader is introduced to the world inside the Wall and partakes in it through the eyes of Kavanagh. He gradually undergoes a psychological shift, moving from identifying as a defender to seeing himself as an outsider, which is reflected in his words, actions, and inner thoughts. Kavanagh's psychological journey, therefore, shapes the trajectory of the novel. In the beginning, Kavanagh is awestruck, witnessing the changing world around him, much like any other character in the novel. The defenders eloquently portray the boredom, anxiety, fear, and anger experienced by them throughout the novel. Kavanagh's solitary life, along with that of the other characters, makes it evident that the wall is not just a protective barrier, however, it leads human beings to isolate themselves from one another psychologically.

Written in the first-person perspective of the protagonist, Katie, *Not Alone* by Sarah K. Jackson is a compelling exploration of the post-apocalyptic world devastated by environmental calamity, particularly the aftermath of a devastating microplastic storm. This novel investigates the psychological effects of climatic trauma, especially on the relationship between a mother and her child, in addition to telling a compelling survival tale. This narrative showcases the extent to which a parent will go to safeguard their child in an unhealthy and threatening environment, which unfolds as a combination of tormenting survival and an emotional journey fuelled by hope.

According to a new report from the American Psychological Association, climate change can severely impact people's mental health. These health issues can be accelerated when a cold climate acts as a trigger factor. The entire plot of *The Wall* takes place in a cold atmosphere. Lanchester has skilfully woven the 'coldness' to indicate both parlous climatic conditions and a psychological hint. At the beginning of the novel, the narrator describes the condition as "It's cold

as slate, as diamond, as the moon. Cold as charity - that's a good one... It's nothing but a physical fact. This kind of cold, anyway. Cold is cold is cold.” (Lanchester 3).

Jackson uses the inner darkness of despair to reveal a complex relationship between the harsh reality evoked by the cold climate and the fear of an uncertain world. “The horrible dark despair of last winter yawns open inside me” (Jackson 14). The motifs of ‘cold’ in *The Wall* and the ‘winter’ in *Not Alone* reveal the inner darkness of despair and the complex relationship between the harsh realities. Such anxiety reflects the general anxiety humanity experiences, driven by a deep-seated fear for oneself and environmental degradation. Coldness associated with winter can often be interpreted as the emotional coldness that accompanies fear and dread about the future.

Constant exposure to appalling coldness numbs human emotions. This changes man’s outlook towards the environment, making them emotionally numb. The evolution of the ecology from a land of flora to a barren, cold desert has critically impacted the creative intellect of the protagonist. Such emotional numbness in the protagonist is depicted visually through short poems in the novel, transitioning from the shape of a tree to a block of concrete, and finally to a Japanese haiku.

a
poem
about a
tree in the
shape of a tree,
in this case a Christ-

mas tree, not a very con-
vincing tree and not a very good
poem but it's not trying to be a death-
less masterpiece it's just to show the idea
yes?

(Lanchester 13)

concrete concrete concrete concrete concrete
concrete concrete concrete concrete concrete

(Lanchester 15)

sky!
cold
water
concrete
wind

(Lanchester 16)

These shifting shapes capture the change that has ensued after a disastrous climate occurrence, made of “concretewaterskywindcold.” This lack of space represents the impending wall that divides and suffocates the citizens, forcing them to be climate migrants. The strict rules of the regime suffocate the citizens, leading them to feel oppressed. This deprives them of having personal space and the freedom to think, decide, and act independently. Inmates inside the wall experience extreme suffocation, leading to profound effects on their mental states by shaping their perceptions and behaviours. Such an environment creates a sense of acute psychological isolation in them.

While climate change casts a bleak influence over Kavanagh's creative intellect, Katie's description of the world outside appears as an attempt to find hope in an otherwise hopeless reality.

Eyes scanning the same flat hard ground that always looks up at me from four floors below, snaked with algae and moss. The same grey buildings that press in on us all around, with dappled ivy-strewn alleys running between them. (Jackson 1)

Through this description of post-disaster buildings and alleys, *Not Alone* captures how ecological and artificial systems are intertwined. Although individuals initially experience despair in the aftermath, they also begin forming new community constructs and fostering the social connections necessary for recovery. Dappled, ivy-strewn alleys symbolise new growth and the recuperation efforts through which nature can restore space and offer hope amid the devastation. Environmental impacts of catastrophic events contribute to developing greater resilience and adaptability among urban populations.

When significant changes or degradation occur in familiar environments, individuals or communities may experience a loss of their sense of belonging. Glenn Albrecht, an environmental philosopher, introduced the term ‘solastalgia’ as the distress and isolation caused by the gradual removal of solace from the present state of one’s home environment. The Latin word "solas" means comfort, and the Greek word "algos" means pain. Such blending emphasizes the pain associated with losing one's sense of place and belonging.

Add in the fact that so much of the time, what you're mainly looking at is concrete. You stand on it, you sleep in it, your home and office and the place you eat and the place you shit and the place that gets in your dreams - concrete. Concrete... there it is again. (Lanchester 14)

The ‘concrete’ surrounding the inmates is, in fact, their physical and psychological confinement, which serves as a constant reminder imposed by the environment. Such an atmosphere can intensify the isolation and create a sense of entrapment. Absence of natural landscapes, open skies, and fresh air intensifies this feeling, depriving people of the essential sensory experiences necessary for their well-being. This disconnection from nature is a poignant reminder of the declining nature-human relationship. It can lead man to a chronic stress response with an increased secretion of the primary stress hormone, cortisol, causing extreme fear and anxiety.

Katie expresses her sense of entrapment by stating, “I feel a little better now I’m inside again, yet worry still makes me double-check that the smashed windows on the ground floor are still barricaded.”(Jackson 40). Psychological impact of solastalgia on Katie becomes particularly evident here through her behaviours and thoughts. One can also evaluate it through her occasional recollections of life before the storm. Katie’s preoccupation with ensuring that their apartment is secure reflects a more immense existential fear that results from realising that everything around

has altered forever. It reveals the extent of environmental degradation, which not only poses a physical threat but also shatters people's emotional ties to their homes and surroundings, leaving them mourning what they have lost. Also, Katie's struggle represents the deep sorrow of seeing her once-vibrant surroundings now dying slowly. Her natural tendency to shield Harry from harm emphasises her will to persevere.

Human beings' ability to remain resilient in the face of adversity allows them to cultivate a sense of 'hope against hope,' a concept from the New Testament of the Bible. Hence, having a sense of purpose positively influences both mental health and the capacity for hope.

Somebody said there was no greater misery than recalling time of happiness when you're in a time of despair, and that's true, but let's focus on the positive and remember that the opposite is also true. (Lanchester 18)

The protagonist, Kavanagh, reminisces about his beautiful and harmonious past and is tormented by his current life of despair. Even though he knows that recalling memories increases the despair, he still tries to stay optimistic in his thoughts. One can also analyse this as the constant mood swings that the inmates experience while isolated in the Wall. Lanchester attempts to encourage readers to understand the Wall as both a literal and figurative barrier erected by societies.

People constantly exposed to threatening climate change problems are also subjected to a psychological response called eco-anxiety. Recent surveys indicate that eco-anxiety has become a widespread concern among people who report feelings of worry, sadness, and powerlessness due to the environmental crisis. It can significantly impact mental health, leading to increased stress, depression, and anxiety symptoms. Psychologists have recognised that uncertainty can contribute

to climate trauma in various ways. Fear of not knowing what happens outside can lead to an extreme state of anxiety compounded by living in a constant environmental threat. This state can exacerbate existing mental health issues and lead to new psychological disorders.

One day was type 2 cold, dangerously cold, frighteningly cold, but the weather forecasters had told us it was coming and we were prepared. The really lethal cold is the kind that comes on when you aren't expecting it. (Lanchester 44)

And then because the Wall is the dominant thing in your life ... and your future life is determined by what happens on the Wall – you can, fairly easily, lose your life here, or lose the life you wanted to have... (Lanchester 14)

The above-mentioned lines depict how unpredictability in the climate leads to a sense of uncertainty in the lives of inmates inside the wall. The uncertainty experienced can cause a wide range of negative emotional responses, making them vulnerable, which further worsens their mental well-being. Essentially, the unpredictability in cold climates symbolises unpredictability in their life. This unanticipated cold compels the individuals to navigate through unexpected conditions and thereby induces fear, anxiety, and an overall feeling of helplessness. Depiction of the wall as the ‘dominant thing’ highlights the dominance of the wall that controls their day-to-day existence. The commitment forced upon the defenders to patrol the cold and concrete expanse for the entire two years led to their loss of individuality, making them purely defined by their role. Therefore, this irrefutable focus on duty fosters a sense of futility that results in forgetting their aspirations and dreams.

Increased uncertainty about the environment can lead to a range of negative emotional responses, leaving individuals feeling powerless and vulnerable, which in turn worsens their

mental well-being. A number of survivors experience chronic distress and difficulties in adaptation due to the fear of irreversible changes in their environment. People frequently experience a sense of overwhelm regarding the future, including concerns about the safety and well-being of themselves, their loved ones, and the surrounding environment.

What happens to him? If I can't forage now in the last of summer and the autumn, can't build enough winter stock, can't get out of bed, can't breathe—I can't finish that thought. There's no one. (Jackson 13,14)

The deep uncertainty surrounding Katie as a mother is brought to light by her reflection. She struggles with the harsh reality that her son's survival depends on her being able to forage for food and prepare enough supplies for the winter. Feeling of abandonment not only reveals Katie's fear about her inadequacy as a caregiver but also highlights the broader societal failure to protect the vulnerable population. Katie embodies a sense of powerlessness, a condition exacerbated by the reality that her generation has actively contributed to the very circumstances from which they now suffer.

How they started to find plastic dust in rivers, soils and even the air – and also in the vast oceans, millions of pieces per square metre, washed there like it was a great big watery garbage dump. (Jackson 388)

The discovery of plastic dust in rivers, soils, air, and the vast oceans not only represents a disaster for the environment but also has a significant effect on the characters' mental health, especially for survivors who are struggling with anxiety. Plastic pollution constantly exposes the characters to the unpredictable nature of their natural environment. As the protagonists understand the extent of pollution and its effects on their health and safety, they experience a sense of

helplessness and worry as once-familiar and stable ecosystems become tainted. The phrase 'a great big watery garbage dump' captures the growing awareness that human-made waste has infiltrated even the most remote parts of the planet. In consequence, the unpredictability of the climate crisis further complicates how the survivor's personal life affects their worsening mental health.

Katie reveals about her difficulty sleeping as she says, "I barely sleep – cold and anxious about dust I can't see, of drifting off and bad rain or wind starting up and coming in..." (Jackson 352). Anxiety, rather than just physical discomfort, mostly causes the sleeplessness mentioned here. It further emphasises how Katie's anxiety regarding the unfamiliar environment prevents her from finding rest. The fear of dust indicates the intangible, unnoticed effects of environmental collapse. The protagonist's fear arises not from a particular incident but from her never-ending concern about her and her son's safety.

The climate-related anxiety and distress expressed by many individuals have dramatically influenced their reproductive choices. Researches show that concerns about environmental stability based on attitudes toward reproduction favour having fewer or no children. Approximately, 23% of U.S. adults aged 18 to 45 indicate that climate change has made them rethink biological children, with many considering having fewer children or adopting instead.

But people don't want to Breed, because the world is such a horrible place. So, as an incentive to get people to leave the Wall, if you reproduce, you can leave. You Breed to leave the Wall. Some people say that this isn't fair to the children, who are born into a world where they have to do time on the Wall in their turn. (Lanchester 35)

In this context, the notion of breeding is imparted as a means to attain freedom. It introduces a mechanism that shapes individual reproductive choices to conform to broader societal goals.

Society considers reproduction as a method to avoid hardship, rather than personal desire. This concept implies the transactional view of life, where having children is a means to an end and not an autonomous choice.

Katie conveys her anxiety regarding breeding: “Yet creatures like this that can reproduce fast, before they succumb, seem more successful at surviving in the world After.” (Jackson 2). In this context, the comparison is made between the survival strategies of organisms and the fear and anxiety about climate change felt by future generations. Being a single mother, Katie feels deeply anxious about the toxic environment her child is exposed to and will inherit. This reflects not only Katie's struggle but also a generational fear shared by the community. The maternal instinct drives her to take risks, much like fast-reproducing animals that enhance the survival of their offspring in uncertain conditions.

Experiencing climate trauma can intensify the feeling of isolation, making a person feel disconnected even from their support system. Researchers identify that social isolation aggravates emotions of hopelessness and despair in those affected by climate-related disasters. This detachment emerges as a physical distance from social support or emotional distance from assistance providers. Cumulative traumas such as population displacement, economic instability from local climate change, and witnessing environmental deterioration can lead to significant emotional suffering.

I felt my eyes fill with tears: the thought that someone was going to stop and talk to me suddenly seemed like the greatest act of compassion and empathy I had ever encountered.
(Lanchester 24)

In a dystopian society defined by fear and separation, Kavanagh represents not just a soldier but also an individual struggling with his disconnection from the world beyond the wall. An oppressive society heightens this disconnection by viewing interaction as dangerous and undesirable. The interaction between individuals and Kavanagh exemplifies human connection amid environmental disarray. Kavanagh's longing for connection becomes a powerful indication of his emotional state. Tears, symbolise sadness and, more significantly, the longing for a rare compassion.

The inner turmoil in Katie's mind becomes evident through her words, "I scream at myself to fight harder. But there's nothing left. So maybe I am a useless bitch. Nothing. After all, I'm nothing to anyone anymore, am I?" (Jackson 217). This highlights the character's inner conflict and isolation, reflecting deep emotional struggles tied to themes of despair, loneliness, and the search for identity amidst environmental degradation. The call to 'fight harder' reflects an inner conflict between the desire to make a difference and the pervasive sense of futility. The self-directed insult 'useless bitch' reveals a profound internalised sense of failure and worthlessness. In the face of a climate crisis, individuals may experience both physical and mental isolation, fighting external circumstances and an internal battle regarding self-worth. In essence, the given excerpt serves as a commentary on the individual feelings of isolation and societal disconnection due to the climate crisis.

Traumatic events cannot be limited to just stressful experiences. However, they are situations that extend beyond the capacity of an individual to comprehend and interpret things, typically concerning dangers to life or bodily integrity. It disrupts one's sense of internal trust and safety, which leads to a warped view of the outside world and oneself. Dissociation, one such typical trauma response, results in a disconnection from reality, causing feelings of detachment.

Collective dissociation is a pivotal element within the intricate interplay between the psyche and climate change, highlighting its profound and nonlinear nature. Responses such as dissociation, denial, fear, and misinformation contribute significantly to people's resistance towards climate action concerning its psychological, social, cultural and political factors.

Dissociation is a significant subject in *The Wall* through factors like the generational divide, the emotional toll of loneliness, and the characters' alienation from reality. Distancing oneself from the idea of home indicates a disconnection with past convictions and interests. Moreover, the wall's monotonous surroundings and persistent cold produce an emotional numbness, which is a sign of dissociation. Blame and guilt over the state of the world trigger a glaring gap and alienation between the younger and older generations. The detachment and emotional distress due to the post-apocalyptic environment outside show an implicit indication of dissociation. The constant threat of the poisoned world and encounters with dangerous survivor contributes to a sense of detachment from their former lives and selves. Katie's post-traumatic stress and the overall bleakness of their existence imply dissociation as a form of survival mechanism.

While climate change negatively affects living conditions overall, its most harmful and often overlooked consequences are on human psychology. Climate change-related events can result in trauma similar to traumatic stress. Addressing the mental health implications of climate change requires understanding the direct and indirect pathways that affect individuals and communities. The climate fiction novels inspire readers to engage with their communities and take action against climate change. Quintessentially, climate fiction imparts awareness regarding climate change and its societal impacts, encouraging discussions about climate policies, ethics, and personal responsibilities. Its depiction of relatable characters and scenarios motivates readers to realise their role in combating climate change. Reviews based on such novels act as a bridge

between literature and the public, promoting a deeper understanding and engagement with climate issues.

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